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Research Article

**QT INTERVAL IN MULTIDRUG RESISTANT TUBERCULOSIS
REGIMENS: DOES EARLY PREDICTIONS OF
PROLONGATION IN QT INTERVAL OFFERS ANY HELP?****Smitha Thungathurthi, Orsu Prabhakar Ph.D**Department of Pharmacology,
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Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh, India.**Article Received:** October 2020 **Accepted:** November 2020 **Published:** December 2020**Abstract:**

India stands on the top position in the incidences of new cases of drug sensitive and resistant tuberculosis. Treatment for any ailment contemplates drug safety and patient benefits. Prolongation in QT interval is considered as one of the potential adverse effects with anti-tubercular drugs. Being asymptomatic, it is considered as one of the endpoints for cardiac safety in pharmacovigilance where it sometimes may lead to syncope and sudden cardiac death in an hour reported in few cases. The prolongation in QT interval appears to be overlooked in clinical practice which is of the major concern to look into. Generally, the treatment in multidrug resistant tuberculosis (MDRTB) includes at least one QT interval prolonging drug in the regimen. This review helps in identifying the extent of QT interval prolongation with multi drug resistant tuberculosis regimens. Manuscripts determining the antitubercular drugs involved in QT interval lengthening and few describing the health factors for the same taken into consideration in this review. QT interval prolongation ascertained with the antitubercular drugs such as levofloxacin, moxifloxacin, clofazimine, bedaquiline and delamanid along with these agents confounding factors also play a key role. Hence, predictive analyses in developing clinical decision tools are essential for health professionals. Priority to enhance for providing interventions based on evidence management in reducing the QT interval prolongation is a prerequisite.

Keywords: Multi-drug resistant tuberculosis, QT interval, Electrocardiogram, QT interval prolonging drugs, risk factors.

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INTRODUCTION:

QT interval makes the ventricle more susceptible to premature electrical impulses or early after-depolarization leading to polymorphic ventricular tachycardia or the twisting of QRS complexes around isoelectric baseline represented as Torsade de pointes (TdP). This generally occurs in congenital form or drug induced. There are many categories of drugs prolonging QT interval. Treatment for any ailment contemplates drug safety and patient benefits. Lengthening of QT interval in the electrocardiogram has been one of the potential adverse effects with drugs involved. Being asymptomatic QT interval prolongation is considered as one of the endpoints for cardiac safety in pharmacovigilance where it sometimes may lead to syncope and sudden cardiac death in an hour reported in few cases. The prolongation in QT interval appears to be overlooked in clinical practice which is of the major concern to look into. QT interval measurement includes from the initiation of QRS complex to the end of T wave in the leads II, V5, V6 of the electrocardiogram. Abnormal QT interval makes the ventricle more susceptible to premature electrical impulses or early after-depolarization leading to polymorphic ventricular tachycardia or the twisting of QRS complexes around isoelectric baseline represented as Torsade de pointes (TdP). The clinical manifestations include heart rate between 160-240 beats per minute, palpitations, dizziness, lightheadedness, shortness of breath, near syncope and syncope. Syncope lasts for a very short period and sometimes degenerates into ventricular fibrillation resulting in sudden cardiac death (SDC).¹ Generally the corrected QT interval calculated utilizing Bazette, Fredericia, Framingham or Hodges formulae. The reference range of QTc interval for men is 350-450milli seconds (ms) and 360-460ms in women or a delta QTc (difference between the baselines of two QTc in a sequence) of ≥ 30 ms for moderately prolonged and $QTc \geq 500$ ms in men or a delta $QTc \geq 60$ ms for severely prolonged. The

American organization credible Meds enlists the drugs with known risk for QTc prolongation periodically.²

MDRTB treatment includes at least one QT interval prolonging drug in its regimen. QT interval prolongation ascertained with the antitubercular drugs such as levofloxacin, moxifloxacin, clofazimine,³ bedaquiline^{3,4} and delaminid.^{3,5} This review helps in identifying the extent of QT interval prolongation causing antitubercular drugs and gives an insight on its contributing factors.

METHODS:

The systematic review of literature performed according to Preferred Reporting Items for Systemic Reviews and Meta-analysis (PRISMA) statement. The published peer-reviewed, scientific evidence articles searched in Pubmed, EMBASE and Cochrane. The manuscripts obtained using keywords such as QT interval, bedaquiline, moxifloxacin, levofloxacin, Floroquinolones, clofazimine, delaminid, risk factors and scoring with boolean operators AND, OR, NOT. All the manuscripts screened based on the title and the abstract available. Manuscripts' describing the outcome of the QT interval in MDRTB patients and regimens involving these antitubercular drugs was the main concern in selecting. The manuscripts with an inclusion criterion of age above 18 considered. A note on the measures in managing the QT interval described in the review.

A total of n=56 records identified through database searching from the year 2001 to 2020 excluding editorials, abstracts and reviews. The articles dealing with other categories of drugs, community-based scoring of QT interval excluded. The original manuscripts, research articles dealing with antitubercular drugs, case reports, eligible included in this review.

Fig 1: Literature survey (PRISMA 2009 flow chart)

RESULTS:

Antitubercular drugs characterized to have QT interval prolongation in MDRTB regimens are bedaquiline, delamanid, clofazimine, moxifloxacin and levofloxacin. The regimens consist of at least one or more than one QT interval prolonging drug. The drug levofloxacin in isoniazid mono resistant tuberculosis, combination of moxifloxacin and clofazimine in shorter regimen, and bedaquiline, levofloxacin, clofazimine together in all oral longer regimen along with their respective background regimen.³

Table 1: Observed QT interval in patients

First author & Year of publication	Study period & Study design	QT interval prolonging drugs	Observed QT interval prolongation and Remarks
Rohit Sarin, 2019 ⁶	1 st July, 2016 - 31 st Dec, 2018 Prospective cohort N=290	Bedaquiline+clofazimine Bedaquiline+moxifloxacin	n=56 (29.4%) Discontinued bedaquiline =4 Withhold if >500ms
Olatunde olayanju, 2019 ⁷	Jan, 2014- Apr, 2018 Prospective cohort N=122	Bedaquiline alone n=82 Bedaquiline+Delamanid n=40 HIV patients Bedaquiline alone n=42 Bedaquiline+Delamanid n=22 HIV uninfected patients Bedaquiline alone n=40 Bedaquiline+Delamanid n=18	QTc>60ms=06 (7.3%) >450ms=16 (19.5%) QTc>60ms=07 (20.6%) >450ms=15 (44.1%) No >500ms= 0 in both. QTc>60ms=05 (11.9%) >450ms=11 (26.2%) QTc>60ms=04 (18.2%) >450ms=07 (31.8%) No >500ms= 0 in both. QTc>60ms n = 01 (2.5%) >450ms n = 05 (12.5%) QTc>60ms n = 03 (16.6%) >450ms n = 08 (44.4%) No >500ms n = 0 in both.
Rohit Sarin, 2019 ⁸	March, 2017 - 31 st Nov, 2019 Prospective cohort N=53	One or two QT interval prolonging drugs Bedaquiline, Delamanid	QTc>60ms n = 07 (13.2%) QTc>480ms n = 11 (20%) QTc>500ms and >60ms n=1 (1.88%) Of 11 deaths, n=5 (45.45%) reported with prolonged QTc
Jackie Jones, 2019 ⁹	March 2015 – June 2016 Retrospective N=32	Bedaquiline	n=8 n=1 died reported with hypokalemia, hypomagnesemia
STREAM Stage 1, 2018 ¹⁰	Phase 3, open label, randomized controlled study N=271	Shorter regimen	QTc>500ms n=28 (9.9%)
Gabriella Ferlazzo, 2018 ¹¹	1 st Jan, 2016 – 31 st Aug, 2016 Retrospective N=28	Bedaquiline+Delamanid	No QTc>500ms QTc >60ms from baseline n=4 Asymptomatic and no discontinuation of treatment.
Gugliemetti, 2018 ¹²	Dec, 2016 – July 2017 Cross-sectional survey N=61	Bedaquiline/ Delamanid	n=9 (14.75%) Discontinued if QTc>500ms
Marina Tadolini, 2016 ¹³	Case study, follow up	Bedaquiline+Clofazimine	QTc>508ms
Alexander S Pym, 2016 ¹⁴	20 th Aug, 2009 – 27 th Sep, 2010 Phase 2 Open label, Single arm trial N=233	Bedaquiline+Clofazimine	n=10 (4.3%) QTc>500ms n=2 deaths Hypokalemia in n=1 patient.

DISCUSSION:

This review gives an insight on the scientific evidence of the factors involved in QT interval prolongation. Utilizing predictive analysis and enumerating the risk factors clinical decision tools, scoring techniques developed in finding the prolongation in QT interval.

The shorter regimen in combination with high dose moxifloxacin and clofazimine and background regimen observes lengthening of QT interval in the re-visits among subjects. The preferred measures in monitoring the patients comprise dose alterations of the moxifloxacin, clofazimine or changing to levofloxacin and discontinuing clofazimine. Early predictions and monitoring the subjects reduces the incidence of side effects.¹⁵

A study analysis in the patients diagnosed with tuberculosis categorized patients into two groups. One group of patients on first line antitubercular drugs and the other prescribed with moxifloxacin 400mg and background regimen. It observes similar and normal mean QTc in the two groups on the follow-up monitoring. Only one patient developed QTc>487ms with no cardiac events or arrhythmia, for which moxifloxacin discontinued permanently. No statistical significance with the increment in QTc for four months. No impact of the factors such as age, gender, body mass index, sputum positive grading and involvement of lung zones on QTc interval but there was a significant variation in both the groups. The study revealed Moxifloxacin 400mg as safe in its prolong usage.¹⁶ Similar to this, a retrospective study on tuberculosis patients determining the safety of moxifloxacin 400mg observes no QT interval prolongation. But the study observes prominent QT prolongation in female gender.¹⁷ The female gender observes lengthened QTc interval in regimens with

floroquinolone. Regular monitoring of QT interval in women on treatment is required. Prolongation in QT interval associates with the influencing factors such as female gender, advancing age, anti-retroviral therapy, and an increment in body mass index. Elevation in body temperature and alteration in serum potassium levels results in shortened QTc with no statistically significance.¹⁸

An integrated study on occurrence of the event, Torsade de pointes among patients administered with non-cardiac drugs like antimicrobials, fluoroquinolones, antimalarials, macrolides), antipsychotics, antihistamines. In most of the subjects' prescribed non-cardiac drugs develop QTc prolongation in three days or in a month and above. Risk factors like gender, history of heart related disease, electrolyte imbalance, drug interactions, reduced clearance and simultaneous utilization of more than one QT interval drugs should be ascertained with control group for a proper identification of people who are at risk of QTc prolongation.¹⁹ Study noticed females are the most vulnerable group for unknown reason and following evaluation of cardiovascular and non-vascular drugs noticed QTc interval >500ms in both classified groups.²⁰

A retrospective study for the condition of QT interval in the patients treated with levofloxacin illustrates the lengthening of QT interval in few subjects. The factors such as age, gender, body temperature, current status of tobacco products associates with QTc prolongation. The findings report no variation in the patients receiving levofloxacin while the lengthening of QTc observed in a combination of drugs for health ailments along with levofloxacin.²¹

Table 2: Factors predicted to be involved in prolonging the QT interval

Anthropometric measures	Biochemical investigations	Comorbidities
Advanced age	Electrolyte imbalances	Kidney dysfunction
Female gender	Altered liver function tests	Cardiovascular disorders
Obesity	Serum creatinine	Neurological disorders
Drug induced	C-reactive protein	Thyroidal illness

Role of scoring in early predictions of prolongation in QT interval

Predictive analytics helps in unfolding the factors that influence the QT interval. The tool Risk path score predicts the patients at higher and lower risk of QTc prolongation. The score outlines the influence of various risk factors such as comorbidities (diabetes, hypertension, arrhythmia, cardiovascular and neurological disorders), biochemical parameters, electrolyte imbalances, altered liver function, C - reactive protein, drug-drug interactions, anthropometric measures (age, gender, body mass index) on QTc interval. This score helps to preclude the patients at greater risk of QTc prolongation with a predictive value of 98% and assures for the patients safety. No significant difference between baseline QTc and its follow-up assuring elimination of the patients from follow-up.²² With the same strategy of finding the probable risk factors of QT interval prolongation a pro-QT score developed in a retrospective study. Such clinical decision tools helps in alerting for a proper management in presence of at least one risk factor. The utilization of QTc interval prolonging drugs, clinical conditions and electrolyte disturbances observes as the predominant causes of lengthening.²³ These evaluation tools support in early screening of the patients, predicting the patients at risk. Such scores stratify various clinical conditions, laboratory investigations, prescribed medicine, anthropometric objectives. Attaining patient benefits by choosing the right drugs for any asymptomatic lengthening of QT interval prolongation, their monitoring reduce the risk.²⁴

Despite the intense knowledge on the prolongation in QT interval, monitoring requires the detection of identifiable risk factors. Developing algorithm, clinical scores necessitates filling the gap of ascertaining the determinants involved. A pro-QT score developed enumerating the risks and electrocardiograms (ECGs). The measures of QRS ≤ 120 ms and QTc ≥ 500 ms and heart rate ≤ 100 beats per minute as one criteria and the other with QRS ≥ 120 ms heart rate ≤ 100 beats per minute with a QTc ≥ 550 ms obtained to stratify the risks. The drugs involved in prolonging the QT interval, electrolyte disturbances of potassium, calcium and magnesium contributes the prolongation in QT interval and all-cause mortality. The existing medical conditions have less influence in QT prolongation. The developed pro-QTc score well recognize the patients at the higher risk possibility of mortality comparatively. Monitoring the patients by modifying the factors involved such as medications and correcting the electrolytes reduces the lengthening. Outlining the predictors, helps in managing the patients with the

early interventions by scoring.²⁵ Scores developed based on the predictive analytics utilizing electronic medical records, data mining available from various departments such as cardiovascular, renal, infectious, pulmonary, cardiovascular, gastrointestinal, psychiatry etc. The various available risk stratification scores for QT interval prolongation illustrated in the Table 3. These scores assists health care team, alerting for the well-being of the patients.

Table 3: Risk stratification scores available for QT interval prolongation

Author	Score
Eline Vandael et.al ²²	Risk Path score
James E Tisdale et.al ²⁴	QT interval risk score
Mayoclinic ²⁵	pro-QT score

Potential measures to reduce QTc

Detailed medical history, medications of the subjects, monitoring the patients comparing the baseline QTc and follow-up ECGs is essential. Measures of QT prolongation repeated for every 30min on initiation of treatment in a confirmed subject. The coexisting clinical conditions and the medications that potentiate the QT effect, necessitates their management to reduce the risk. Presuming to discontinue the drugs in arrhythmias, QTc > 500 ms for the beneficial improvement of the health. The rationale prescribing of QT interval prolonging drugs in check with comorbidities reduces the risk. A necessary correction of serum electrolyte imbalances normalizes the QT interval. The serum electrolytes mostly with respect to potassium, calcium, magnesium, corrections are recommended.^{26,27,28} Replacing the drugs with an alternative drug, making dose alterations, total discontinuation of the drugs is much preferable. In case of rhythmic disturbances, administration of intravenous Magnesium sulphate 1 to 2 g over 15 min, continuous intravenous infusion of Isoproterenol 2 to 10 μ g/min, or rapid pacing stabilizes the rhythmic disturbances of heart.²⁹ Antiretroviral drug efavirenz potentiates the QT effect hence, review the prescription for the change of the drug into nevirapine or protease inhibitors³⁰ or integrase strand transfer inhibitor.³¹ Raised blood glucose levels,³² low blood glucose levels,³³ drug induced hypoglycemia, insulin analogs,³⁴ sulfonylureas,³⁵ prolong QTc, hence counsel the diabetics for a check on healthy blood glucose levels. Monitor drug clearance of clofazimine in renal dysfunction as it lengthens QT interval.³⁶ Finding the arrhythmias and monitoring the patients with dose adjustments establishing normal thyroid stimulating hormone levels in thyroidal illness for hypothyroid,^{37,38} hyperthyroid³⁹ recommended.

Predicting the alterations in liver function tests, renal function tests and thyroid function test, serum calcium along with the clinical evaluations for symptoms such as palpitations, syncope essential.^{26,40}

CONCLUSION:

Predictive analyses used to develop clinical decisions are essential for the health professionals to be vigilant on the factors that lengthen QT interval. Risk factors in managing QT interval are to be ascertained with the evidence based approach for future perspectives. Cost-benefit analysis and health outcomes to be analyzed to implement the clinical decision support tools in health sector. Multi drug resistant tuberculosis patients should be monitored for alterations QT interval as a part of pharmacovigilance for the safety of the patients. Priority to enhance interventions, based on evidence management in reducing the QT interval prolongation is a prerequisite.

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